

Developing a Pressure Sensor for 3D Nonwoven Assemblies by Using Novel Spacer Stitching Technology

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Abstract: Textile-based sensors are gaining attention due to their low cost, light weight, flexibility, and adaptability to a variety of human bodies in comparison to traditional solid-state sensors. These advantages make them a valid alternative for various applications in the field of wearable technology. Textile-based sensors can be developed using conductive polymers, conductive threads, and fabrics depending on the application field. Briefly, textile-based sensors can be designed and used in many different forms and applications. One of these designs is the use of sewing thread as a pressure sensor. In this study, a novel sewing technology called spacer stitching was used to transmit signals through the fabric. This stitching technology avoids material compression during the sewing process, which helps the material maintain its thickness. The spacer stitch sewing method has applications in sewn-through sewing for clothing to improve thermal insulation as well as in spacer fabrics. The pressure sensor was created by sewing conductive thread onto spacer fabric and sandwich-structured nonwoven fabrics using the spacer stitch technology.

Keywords: spacer stitching, nonwoven, textile-based sensors, conductive thread (keywords)

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a remarkable surge in interest surrounding wearable technology, particularly in textile-based sensors. Textile-based sensors are gaining attention due to their low cost, light weight, flexibility, and adaptability to a variety of human bodies in comparison to traditional solid-state sensors. These advantages make them a valid alternative for various applications in the field of wearable technology [1]. Textile-based sensors are used for tracking heart rate [2] and body temperature [3], as well as recording details of sports activities such as walking and running [4]. Textile-based sensors are categorized into subgroups such as piezoelectric, resistive, and capacitive based on their working mechanisms [5]. Textile-based sensors can be developed using conductive polymers, conductive threads, and fabrics depending on the application field. Briefly, textile-based sensors can be designed and used in many different forms and applications. One of these designs is the use of sewing thread as a signal carrier.

Stitch-based sensors are a type of sensor integrated directly into the fabric using conductive sewing threads. Alshabouna et al. developed a textile-based sensor using a computerized embroidery machine and conductive cotton threads. These sensors were integrated into various textile surfaces, such as masks, and t-shirts, and were utilized for applications in heartbeat and breathing monitoring [6]. Choudhry et al. designed a textile-based piezoresistive sensor using conductive threads sewn onto fabric [7]. The stitch-based sensor has a multi-layered structure consisting of fabric, a flexible conductive sheet, and a semi-rigid material. Another study conducted by Choudhry et al. integrated the stitch-based sensor into the clothing [8]. Thus, the sensor analyzed the changes in muscle pressure during sports activities. Furthermore, it was emphasized that when the cyclist wears the sensor-embedded clothing, the sensor can detect the change in speed.

The use of sewing threads as sensors has attracted the attention of researchers due to its low production cost, easy production method, and free-form design advantages. Tangsirinaruenart et al. developed a flexible and wearable stitch-based sensor by sewing conductive threads onto the fabric using a sewing machine. They created different stitch geometries with the sewing machine and investigated the sensing properties of these sensors [9]. Zhang et al. designed gloves by using commercial fabrics and threads, turning them into electric heaters that can be cut/sewn/woven [10]. Park et al. developed a strain sensor capable of detecting human body joint movements by sewing conductive threads onto various textile substrates such as knit fabric and woven fabric [11].

In this study, a novel sewing technology called spacer stitching was used to transmit signals through the fabric. The technology is developed to address the known problem of sewing compressions along stitch lines. This stitching technology avoids material compression during the sewing process, which helps the material maintain its thickness. The spacer stitch sewing method has applications in sewn-through sewing for clothing to improve thermal insulation as well as in spacer fabrics [12], [13]. The sensor was created by sewing conductive thread onto spacer fabric and sandwich-structured nonwoven fabrics using the spacer stitch technique. In brief, conductive threads are used as a pressure sensor.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Employed Materials

The conductive thread used in the study is Silver-tech+, by AMANN Group in Germany. Silver-tech+ is utilized for conductive seams and surfaces. It is a special sewing thread with a silver coating and has a fully conductive

surface. Silver-tech+ has a fineness of 33 tex and its resistance is $< 200 \Omega/\text{m}$.

The used needle thread is Saba polyester thread, by AMANN Group, Germany. It is a core spun yarn which has a high abrasion resistance and strength properties. Two types of Saba polyester thread are used as needle thread in this study which are white color 100 tex thread and red color 120 tex thread.

2.2 Needle-punched nonwoven fabric

In this study, needle-punched nonwoven fabric was created using hollow PET fibers and short milkweed fibers (SMF). The SMFs were provided by Pangai Materials Science in Italy. Measurement of at least 50 individual SMF lengths under an optical microscope revealed an average fiber length of $2.13 \pm 1.4 \text{ mm}$ and a diameter of $25.35 \pm 3.7 \mu\text{m}$. The hollow PET fibers, supplied by SASA Polyester Sanayi A.Ş. in Turkey, have a staple length of 64 mm and a fineness of 6.7 denier. Both types of fibers were utilized in their received condition without any further processing.

To create a carded web, 50 g of PET fibers were manually fed into a 337A Mesdan laboratory carding machine. The carding machine's feeding conveyor belt is 43 cm width, while the end roller is 48 cm width, operating at a speed of 10 m/min. For the blended web, the produced PET carded web was cut in half, with one half placed on the carding machine's conveyor belt. Then, 50 g of SMFs were evenly distributed on this web, and the other half of the PET web was placed on top of the SMFs. This sandwich-like assembly was then fed into the carding machine. The resulting carded web was taken from the end roller, rotated 90° , and fed into the carding machine again to ensure homogeneous SMF distribution.

The needle punching was performed using a Cormatex S.R.L needle punching machine, which has 2080 needles on plates that are 104 cm wide. Notched needles penetrated the web from both the top and bottom at a 90° angle, thoroughly intertwining the fibers to produce needle-punched nonwovens. The needle punching machine operated at 354 strokes per minute from the top and 351 strokes per minute from the bottom, with a punching depth set at 10 mm from both the top and bottom strokes.

The Spacer fabric used was made of polyester with a thickness of 1 cm.

2.3 Sewing method of spacer stitching

Spacer stitching is a novel sewing technology that has been developed at ITM, TU Dresden [14], [15]. The technology is developed to address the known problem of sewing compressions along stitch lines. In this spacer stitching joining method for 3D nonwoven assembly, the outer layers of fabric are spaced apart and material compression during sewing is avoided.

Figure 1 illustrates the concept of spacer stitching using the principle of lockstitch sewing technology (Class 301). The needle and bobbin thread interlace with each other in the middle of the 3D assembly, yet they maintain a rectangular shape and a three-dimensional stitch formation is realized at the point of needle insertions.

Figure 1 Spacer Stitch diagram to create uncompressed stitch formation

To create samples for signal transmission, the samples are prepared with spacer stitching. Sensors thread has already been used by using sewing technology in wearable electronics as well in technical textile applications. The signal-carrying sensor thread works as an element which carries signals and at the end joins with some sensor. The novel idea of using spacer stitching is to use sewing thread not only to carry electrical signals, but also as a technology, which gives signal information when external forces are applied to 3D assemblies.

The spacer stitching prototype uses lockstitch sewing technology (Class 301) for making stitches. The sensor thread is used in bobbin as it experiences less frictional forces during stitch formation.

2.4 Spacer stitching of nonwoven fabric

The spacer stitching technique was used to obtain pressure buttons from sandwich-structured nonwoven fabric. For this purpose, two specimens were cut into $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}$ rectangles from needle-punched PET/SMF blended nonwoven fabric. A sandwich structure was obtained by placing nonwoven filling material which has a $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}$ rectangle shape between these two pieces.

For the sewing process, Saba polyester thread was used as needle thread, while silver-tech+ conductive thread was used as bobbin thread. It is known that the interlacing point of the needle and bobbin thread can be shifted by adjusting the needle and bobbin thread sewing tensions. The interlacing point is shifted towards the bobbin thread which is the sensor thread. The needle thread is shown in grey and the red thread is the sensor thread which is the bobbin thread. The tension of the red thread is more than the grey thread, therefore interlacing point is shifted towards it.

This concept is used to make smart textile applications using spacer fabric as well as milkweed nonwoven assembly.

The optimum thread tension was manually adjusted so that the interlacings of these two threads were close to the bobbin thread. After adjusting the thread tension, the sandwich-structured nonwoven fabric was sewn according to the stitch design. Thus, while the needle thread is seen on the upper surface of the fabric, the conductive thread is sewn on the back surface. After the sewing process of the front surface was completed, the back surface of the fabric was turned and the sewing process was performed again with the same stitch design over the same stitch lines. This is explained in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Sewing the second stitch line on the previous one after switching sides

The conductive threads are sewn on the front and back sides of the conventional spacer fabric with the same spacer stitching sewing method. Interlacement points and needle threads remaining between the fabric can be seen in Figures 3a and 3b.

3 RESULTS

To show these fabrics can be used as pressure sensors, the sewn sandwich-structured nonwovens were integrated into the electrical circuit. For this purpose, the conductive thread on the front surface of the fabric was fixed to the negative pole of the battery, and the conductive thread on the back surface of the fabric was fixed to the negative pole of the LED. Another conductive thread was cut to an optimum length and then it was fixed to the positive poles of the battery and the LED. Thus, the simple electrical circuit is completed and shown in Figure 3, the diagram illustrates the open and closed switch states of the electrical circuit with sandwich-structured nonwoven fabric.

Figure 3 Illustration of the sandwich-structured nonwoven pressure sensor. The nonwoven fabric can be utilized as an open switch when released (a), and as a closed switch when gripped (b).

When force was applied to the sandwich-structured nonwoven fabric within the electrical circuit, the interlacing points of upper and lower stitch lines came into contact with each other which were held apart by spacer stitching. As a result, it was observed that current flowed through the circuit. When the force acting on the fabric was removed,

the LED turned off, indicating that no current was passing through the circuit.

The samples were also made with spacer fabrics. With the application of external forces, the sensor threads sewn with spacer stitching came into contact and signals were transmitted. By removal of external forces, the circuit was disconnected by inherent forces of spacer fabrics and interlacing point of spacer stitching went apart. As a result, the current flow stopped.

Figure 4 Electric circuit when spacer fabric (a,b) and sandwich-structured nonwoven fabric (c,d) are released and gripped.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, we explored the development and application of textile-based pressure sensors using a novel sewing technique known as spacer stitching. This method effectively addresses the common issue of material compression during the sewing process, thereby preserving the thickness and integrity of the fabric. By employing conductive thread sewn onto spacer fabric and sandwich-structured nonwoven fabrics, we successfully created a pressure sensor that combines flexibility, durability, and high sensitivity. Future research will focus on further optimizing the sensor design and exploring additional applications to fully leverage the benefits of this technology.

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